

Surgical Management of Chylothorax: A Paediatric Case Series in Georgetown Public Hospital Corporation, 2023

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Abstract

Background: Pediatric chylothorax is an uncommon but clinically significant condition that can lead to substantial morbidity. Management strategies vary, particularly in low-resource settings where advanced interventional options may be unavailable.

Objective: To describe the clinical presentation, diagnostic considerations, and surgical management of pediatric chylothorax in a tertiary referral center in Guyana.

Methods: We report a prospective case series of three pediatric patients diagnosed with chylothorax at Georgetown Public Hospital Corporation in 2023. Clinical data, imaging, biochemical findings, and operative details were collected and analyzed descriptively.

Results: Three patients with differing underlying etiologies developed chylothorax. Initial conservative management was implemented in all cases but was insufficient to achieve sustained resolution. All patients subsequently underwent thoracic duct ligation, with adjunctive pleurodesis using benzylpenicillin. Resolution of chylous effusion was observed in all cases, with no immediate postoperative complications documented.

Conclusion: In this small case series, thoracic duct ligation was associated with favorable outcomes in pediatric patients with persistent chylothorax following failed conservative management. These findings should be interpreted cautiously given the limited sample size and descriptive nature of the study. Further research is needed to evaluate optimal management strategies, particularly in resource-constrained settings.

Keywords: Chylothorax; Pediatric; Thoracic duct ligation; Low-resource setting; Pleurodesis

Introduction

Chylothorax, also known as chylous pleural effusion, is a rare condition characterised by the accumulation of lipid-rich chyle in the pleural cavity due to thoracic duct damage. The causes can be traumatic or non-traumatic, and aetiology differs in adults and children. In adults, thoracic trauma and tumours are predominant, while in children, postoperative complications of cardiothoracic surgery are most common [1-5].

The gold standard of diagnosis has been by direct visualization or lymphangiography, while others rely on analyzing the triglyceride and cholesterol levels in the pleural fluid obtained through thoracentesis [6]. A triglyceride level greater than 110 mg/dL highly indicates a chylothorax while 15% of patients may have a level less than 110 mg/dL and another 3% have values less than 50 mg/dL [7].

The objectives in managing these individuals are to identify and address the root cause, be it autoimmune disorders, malignancy, cirrhosis, or other underlying pathologies. This involves implementing effective pleural drainage, promoting bed rest, and employing a multidisciplinary approach to medical management. Dietary modifications, such as incorporating medium-chain triglycerides, total parenteral nutrition (TPN), or adopting a low-fat regimen, are crucial components of the treatment plan. Additionally, certain medications, including somatostatin and octreotide, demonstrate potential benefits in slowing the chyle flow rate, alongside the use of stool softeners like mineral oil [8-10].

Other invasive procedures have been tried after failure of a thoracic duct ligation such as pleuroperitoneal shunting and pleurovenous shunting in limited numbers [11,12].

This case series report aims to contribute to the existing knowledge on the surgical management of chylothorax in pediatric patients in a low-resource setting.

Case Reports

Case report 1:

A 4-year-old male of mixed race, was admitted on January 26, 2023, with an admitting diagnosis of bronchopneumonia accompanied by bronchospasm, asthma, and moderate respiratory distress leading to respiratory alkalosis. The parent provided a history indicating a previous medical episode of respiratory distress at 6 months, necessitating intubation for 12 days. The current presentation included a 1-week history of subjective fever, non-resolving respiratory distress, productive cough, non-projectile vomiting, and recent onset of shortness of breath.

The patient's past medication history included Amoxicillin, Panadol, and Gravol. Notably, the patient had undergone ligation of the posterior aortic ring for a double aortic arch on January 31, 2023, and subsequent non-diagnostic endoscopy on February 5, 2023, for an upper gastrointestinal bleed. However, a laparotomy involving gastrotomy and pyloroplasty was performed for mucosal bleeding, and an upper endoscopy identified distal esophagitis (esophageal candidiasis) with mild erythema and erosive pangastritis.

Physical examinations reported harsh breath sounds with wheezing bilaterally. Imaging studies included a contrast-enhanced axial scan of the neck revealing a small parapharyngeal abscess, marked pansinusitis, and right mastoid opacification. An abdomen and pelvis ultrasound on January 30, 2023, indicated UTI/cystitis with the urinary bladder. MRI of the brain on February 9, 2023, showed no abnormalities, and Doppler of both lower limbs on February 20, 2023, showed no DVT.

Cytology results indicated several biochemical parameters, including thyroid function, electrolytes, renal function, liver function, and blood counts. The patient tested negative for COVID-19 and TB by gene Xpert. Culture showed no growth after 48 hours. Triglyceride and cholesterol levels were measured at 161 mg/dL and 32 mg/dL, respectively. LDH was recorded at 180 U/L, and protein levels were 5.44 g/dL.

On further management, a chest tube was placed for a pneumothorax which began to drain the chyle on the 22nd of February 2023.

A low-fat diet was continued, and on February 24, 2023, a left thoracic duct ligation was performed for chylothorax leakage. An AP chest x-ray on February 28, 2023, post-thoracic duct ligation, suggested an elevated left hemidiaphragm with lower lobe base opacification likely indicative of associated atelectasis and/or effusion. Medical interventions involved the administration of 4 million units of Benzylpenicillin (Penicillin G) on March 1, 2023, for pleurodesis. The chest tube was removed on March 2, 2023. The patient was discharged on March 6, 2023, by the Cardiothoracic department with instructions for a low-fat diet for 2 weeks and prescribed medication and return to the clinic in 2 weeks. The total

hospitalization duration was 40 days. The patient was given an open date after four weeks post-discharge.

Figure 1. Pre-Op and Post-Op X-ray Report of Case 1

Pre-operative chest radiograph demonstrating left-sided pleural effusion with lung compression (A), and post-operative radiograph showing resolution of effusion and re-expansion of the lung following thoracic duct ligation (B)

Case report 2:

A 15-year-old East Indian female with no previous medical history was brought to the Accident and Emergency Department on 13th Feb. 2023 by her mother, presented with a two-week history of left-sided chest pain, swelling, non-productive dry cough, subjective fever, intermittent shortness of breath (SOB), and decreased appetite. Past medication history included diclofenac and omeprazole. Physical examination revealed dullness to percussion with decreased breath sound over the left upper two-thirds of the lung base. Imaging on 13th Feb. 2023 confirmed left pleural effusion, subcentimeter splenic lesions,

and diffuse ground glass opacities in the left lung. Thoracentesis yielded a 720 ml mixture of white seropurulent fluid.

Cytology on 15th Feb. 2023 showed the following values (Na- 140.6 mmol/L; K- 4.33 mmol/L; Cl- 103.60 mmol/L; BUN- 16.48 mg/dL; Cr- 0.7 mg/dL; LDH serum- 84 U/L; CPK- 35 U/L; T. Bili- 0.4 mg/dL; D. Bili- 0.3 mg/dL; I. Bili- 0.1 mg/dL; ALP-70 U/L; GGT-21 U/L; AST- 54 U/L; ALT 29 U/L; Amylase- 26 U/L; ALB- 3.5 g/dL; Hb- 13.2 g/dL; WBC- $9.21 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$; PH: 3.33). COVID-19 and Gene Xpert TB tests were negative. Triglycerides (98 mg/dL), cholesterol (20 mg/dL), LDH (lactate dehydrogenase, 109 U/L), protein (7,708 mg/dL), and glucose (103 mg/dL) levels were recorded.

Although pleural fluid triglyceride levels (98 mg/dL) were below the conventional diagnostic threshold (>110 mg/dL), the diagnosis of chylothorax was supported by the milky appearance of the fluid, persistent high-output drainage, clinical course, and intraoperative findings. This is consistent with literature indicating that up to 15% of cases may present with triglyceride levels below the diagnostic cutoff.

A left 3-part VATS was performed on 16th Feb. 2023, draining 500ml seropurulent fluid. Notably, after VATS, a suspected chylothorax led to a new diagnosis, and the patient was put on bed rest and Octreotide which was started on the 16th Feb 2023, but held on the 22nd Feb 2023 as the drainage was zero. However, the following day the patient continued to drain 200-400 mls of chyle with a collapsed left lung.

Octreotide was restarted on the 25th Feb 2023 before a left thoracic duct ligation was performed with heavy cream via the NG to determine the site of leak for a spontaneous chylothorax. The exact site of the leak was not seen and duct ligation was done at the level

of the aortic hiatus. Treatment included Octreotide, Benzylpenicillin for pleurodesis, and a low-fat diet. The outcome showed no reaccumulation of fluid after tube removal. The patient was discharged on 8th March 2023, with a prescribed low-fat diet for two weeks and medication, totaling 23 days in the hospital. The patient was given an open date after four weeks post-discharge.

Figure 2. Pre-Op and Post-Op X-ray Report of Case 2

Case Report 3:

A 7-year-old male of mixed race was admitted on April 21, 2023, with a chief complaint of subjective fever, non-projectile vomiting, and green, glossy diarrhea. Previously diagnosed with Tetralogy of Fallot, he had undergone VSD repair, RVOT reconstruction,

and PFO closure a month before admission. Physical examination revealed decreased breath sounds on the left lung base.

Imaging showed left lung expansion. Laboratory results indicated altered urine biochemistry and microscopy, triglycerides at 128 mg/dL, cholesterol at 69 mg/dL, protein at 7,184 mg/dL, and glucose at 111 mg/dL. COVID-19 and Gene Xpert TB tests were negative. An ultrasound-guided pericardiocentesis was performed on April 21, with 240 ml of serosanguinous content removed. Chest tube placement for left pleural effusion, pericardiocentesis for pericardial effusion on April 22. On April 27, 2023, on the table, heavy cream via NG was given however no leak was seen intraoperatively, and a thoracic duct ligation was done at the level of the aortic hiatus. 2.4 million units (2 vials) of injection benzylpenicillin was used with the left thoracic duct ligation (intra-op), and 4.8 million units were given post-op via a chest tube, on May 3, 2023.

The patient was discharged on May 8, 2023, with a low-fat diet recommendation for two weeks and prescribed medication. The total hospital stay was 17 days. The patient fully resolved in the clinic and was given an open date after four weeks post-discharge.

Figure 4. Pre-Op and Post-Op X-ray Report of Case 3

Discussion

There is no universally accepted protocol for chylothorax management, as clinical presentations vary by cause and patient status. Initial management typically includes chest tube drainage, bowel rest, total parenteral nutrition, and fluid replacement [13]. Surgical intervention, such as thoracic duct ligation, is warranted when conservative measures fail or output remains high [3].

Our study found that two-thirds (66.7%) of chylothorax cases were due to a complication of thoracic surgery. This was in line with other studies that reported the most common causes of chylothorax in pediatrics [4, 5, 14]. While few studies have reported successful outcomes with a conservative approach [15, 16, 2] this approach may not be directly applicable to our present study.

In this case series, conservative treatments failed, necessitating surgical ligation with adjunct pleurodesis using Benzylpenicillin (Penicillin G). The use of benzylpenicillin as a pleurodesis agent is not widely reported in pediatric populations and should be considered an institutional adaptation in a resource-limited setting.

While chemical pleurodesis is an established adjunct in persistent pleural effusions, agents such as talc, doxycycline, and bleomycin are more commonly described. In our setting, benzylpenicillin was utilized due to availability and observed clinical response; however, its safety profile and comparative efficacy remain uncertain and warrant further investigation. [17-18]. This approach proved successful in all patients. No immediate adverse reactions were observed in this series; however, the small sample size precludes conclusions regarding safety.

The combination of pleurodesis and duct ligation helps prevent recurrence by promoting pleural adhesion and reducing infection risk.

Figure 4. The Clinical Pathway of Chylothorax Management

In low-resource settings without access to interventional radiology, thoracic duct ligation remains the safest definitive option. [2-3]. Video-assisted thoracoscopic surgery (VATS) is an alternative depending on surgeon experience. Figure 4 shows the clinical pathway of how chylothorax was surgically managed in our institution and is based on our experience and the availability of resources.

This case series explores the rare condition of pediatric chylothorax in Guyana, highlighting personalized treatment strategies and positive patient outcomes. It provides valuable insights for healthcare professionals, students, and researchers on diagnosis, therapy, and decision-making, especially in low-resource settings. While the study offers important baseline regional data and may encourage further research, the findings reflect specific patient experiences and evolving treatment approaches, suggesting the need for continued study to expand understanding and guide broader clinical practice. This study is limited by its small sample size, single-center design, and lack of long-term follow-up. Additionally, variability in underlying etiologies and management strategies limits generalizability.

Conclusion

A multidisciplinary approach is vital in managing paediatric chylothorax. Our experience demonstrates that while conservative treatment remains first-line, definitive surgical intervention through thoracic duct ligation provides successful outcomes in persistent cases.

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Ethical Approval

This case series was conducted in accordance with institutional policy for retrospective case reporting and was formally exempted from ethics committee review. Written informed consent for publication was obtained from the parents/guardians of all patients. All data were anonymized to ensure patient confidentiality.

Funding

Nil.

Conflict of Interest

None declared.

Consent

Written informed consent was obtained from the parents of all patients for publication of this case series and any accompanying data.

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Figure Legends

Figure 1. Pre-Op (A) and Post-Op (B) X-ray Report of Case 1

Figure 2. Pre-Op (A) and Post-Op (B) X-ray Report of Case 2

Figure 3. Pre-Op (A) and Post-Op (B) X-ray Report of Case 3

Figure 4. The Clinical Pathway of Chylothorax Management in a Low-Resource Setting